

Managerial Practices, E-Service Quality, and Organizational Excellence – Empirical Study in Abu Dhabi Municipality

Sharif Omar Salem ^{1*} Younis Abdalmalek Hammouda ²

²Hedef Akaemileri Uluslararası Istanbul, Turkey

Abstract— Purpose: The study aims to empirically examine the influence of different organizational practices on organizational excellence in municipality of Abu Dhabi. E-service quality is examined as mediator and quality of polices is examined as a moderator. **Theoretical Framework:** Activity theory support the assumption that the excellence is a result of the integrated system that encompass the people through their activities and interaction. The proposed conceptual framework includes three dependent variables; employee motivation, knowledge sharing, and collaborative culture. The three variables hypothesized to influence E-service quality as a mediator and organizational excellence as the dependent variable. Besides, quality of polices is hypothesized to moderate the relationship between the mediator and the dependent variable. **Design/Methodology/Approach:** The quantitative research methodology was considered from the positivist philosophical perspective. With the help of the survey questionnaire, data was collected from 335 employees in Abu Dhabi municipality who represent the population of 2500. The data analysis used the PLS-SEM techniques by using the software package SmartPLS ver. 3.0, **Findings:** The results show that employee motivation, knowledge sharing, and collaborative culture are significant antecedents of e-service quality even though e-service quality fails to significantly predict organizational excellence. Also, company quality assurance policy does not moderate the effect of e-service quality on excellence. **Research Practical and Social Implications:** The results are useful for the decision makers in Abu Dhabi municipal and other organizations in the UAE because it shows that the proposed practices have essential impact on the organizational excellence.

Keywords:- E-service quality, Organizational excellence, Abu Dhabi Municipality, Survey.

I. INTRODUCTION

Technology innovation plays a fundamental role in diverse areas of business organizations especially in the public sector service delivery (Bieńkowska et al., 2019). According to Albalate & Bel (2020), the delivery of public services demands critical attention due to the role of these services in meeting the critical needs of the population (Lewis, Nguyen & Hendrawan, 2020). Moreover, unlike private companies, public companies are not inclined to profit-making and are very interested in the area of service excellence and societal improvements. Ultimately, quality has remained a very important subject in public service

delivery (Chanana et al., 2016; Chiravuri & Abdul, 2016). To improve service quality, many technology projects have been introduced within the scope of e-governance and smart government in various public administration reforms (Chiravuri & Abdul, 2016). These projects are mainly targeted at improving service quality and overall public satisfaction with government services (Chanana et al., 2016). Focusing on the area of e-services quality, it was first important to highlight that a strong blend exists between service quality and organizational excellence (Aburayya et al., 2020).

Despite the contribution of e-services to service quality and overall public satisfaction, the alignment between business strategy and technology innovation continues to remain of keen concern for businesses and senior executives (Vasu, 2021). Performance excellence through technology innovation marks the new step in business performance and continues to gain relevance in businesses, particularly in the public domain (Aburayya et al., 2020). Bain et al. (2000, p. 3) on the Ontario Public Service (OPS) Quality Service Model emphasizes that the primary aim of public entities today is to "establish a management model for service excellence". On the emphasized need for alignment between technology and business strategy towards performance, performance excellence in the public sector requires critical attention. As observed by Bryson et al. (2014), the public sector faces many challenges in its efforts to ensure that a representative, competent and professional set of institutions are installed for the national development process. Many governments are therefore implementing innovation policies to transform and revolutionize the sector through public policy frameworks in public value governance (Bryson et al., 2014).

Others have established that the public sector lacks the strategic vision for future advancement and is usually encouraged to adopt measures that exist in the confines of the private sector (Kuipers et al., 2014). Other global and regional bodies have emphasized the need for "high-quality, reliable public services and legal certainty" in the public sector (European Commission 2010, p. 28). The lack of a clear strategic vision breaks the gap in the efforts made by the sector to install organizational excellence through technology innovation. On this background, to achieve excellence in the public sector, earlier studies including Chiravuri & Abdul (2016) on the excellence of e-government services in the UAE, Zaidi & Qteishat (2012) on India e-Government service delivery excellence, among others have emphasized the need for excellence in the public domain through technology innovation and a clear strategy.

Finally, it's crucial to note that Vasu et al. (2021) stressed the importance of integrating institutional strategy with technological innovation in order to achieve organizational excellence.

Building on selected strategy aspects of internal motivation (Oni et al., 2016), knowledge sharing ((Husseini and Fam, 2019 a) and collaborative culture (Nam et al., 2019), the contribution of these areas to e-service quality and organizational excellence are observed (Kim & Kim, 2020). Given the several service quality models proposed, including the service quality model (SERVEQUAL) among others (Zeithaml et al., 2001; Cox & Dale, 2001), the present research builds on the e-service quality model originally proposed by Chiravuri & Abdul (2016) and Zaidi & Qteishat (2012) on measuring e-government service delivery. The overall contribution of key strategies and e-service quality towards organizational excellence are observed (Vasu et al., 2021).

The Abu Dhabi Municipality (Abu Dhabi municipality) is a subsidiary of the Department of Urban Planning and Municipalities (DPM) - Abu Dhabi. DPM remains a key initiator, supporter and driver of the Abu Dhabi Emirate Urban Development Strategy (DPM, 2019). The need to improve e-service quality remains critical to serving the people of Abu Dhabi and its residents. However, like other agencies in the region, technology operationalization and the lack of clear strategy are lagging in their ability to support innovation (Trenwith, 2016). The DPM underlying priorities are spelt in four main areas; these include the need for economic development, social and human resource development, infrastructure development & environmental sustainability, and finally, the optimization of government operations.

To reach these objectives, technology innovation through e-service quality is considered fundamental (DPM, 2019). However, preliminary observation through the organization's mobile application and overall technology innovation reveals significant lapses as less than 1% of customers use the online mobile app. Moreover, employees are less knowledgeable about the application requirements and how to implement installed innovation systems to serve customers. Interest in this area is not new as previous studies, including Badri et al. (2015), Sharaf et al. (2018), and Apostolos & Myrsini (2019), have all looked into service quality and customer satisfaction in the Abu Dhabi Emirate's urbanization attempts. Even though these studies have been useful to the technology transformation of the Abu Dhabi urban system, studies are yet to consider how key elements of corporate strategy can be directed towards e-service quality and organizational excellence. To have a competitive edge in the industry and guarantee posterity and sustainability of the municipalities as one of the internationally recognized municipalities. As a result, this inquiry concentrated on the UAE. In comparison to other Middle Eastern and Arab nations, the public sector in the United Arab Emirates, especially the Municipalities, is more developed and well-established.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Activity theory (AT) appears to offer a descriptive vocabulary for examining in-depth the activity systems where new tools are presented. It is exceptional in this regard due to its all-encompassing approach to the components of human activity. The idea, which takes inspiration from Vygotsky, claims that knowledge is mediated through the actions and interactions of those who utilize it. Activities like thinking, learning, and even knowing are influenced by the activities that people engage in. Through regular engagement in social activities, tools, structures, and working environments are developed. Participation is not feasible without retaining the sociocultural legacy of earlier circumstances. As a result, cognition is rooted in context and history. In addition, the theory offers a mechanism to comprehend how internalization and externalization—two mutually reinforcing processes—cause changes in activity systems. The internal processes that can express outside and organically result in new artefacts and social behaviors are ideas, inventions, and imaginations.

A. Operational Definitions

Organizational excellence is defined as ongoing efforts to develop internal standards and procedures that will engage and motivate personnel to meet customer expectations while maintaining within budgetary restrictions. Wang et al., (2018). The achievement of continuously better performance by an organization, such as outputs that go above and beyond achieving goals, needs, or aspirations (Li & Zhao, 2018).

The enthusiasm, energy level, commitment and the amount of creativity that an employee brings to the organization on a daily basis (Chen & Lin, 202).

A culture of collaboration is one in which cooperation is frequent and intentional (Ahmed et al., 2018). Collaboration does not just begin because someone makes the decision to do so. Instead, it is ingrained in people's daily routines, the way they perform their work, and the attitudes they have toward their jobs.

Knowledge sharing in a company refers to the sharing of valuable information among the members of a company (Chen & Lin, 202). One of the most important things in the process is setting up a company culture that promotes knowledge sharing (Husseini and Fam, 2019 b). Lee (2001) explain knowledge sharing as the action of passing on expertise skill or understanding from an individual, group, firm, or institution to another. Knowledge sharing is the sharing of knowledge among colleagues of an organization within or inside the organization.

A quality policy is a brief statement that outlines the objectives and strategic direction of your company, provides a framework for quality objectives, and includes a commitment to uphold all relevant standards (ISO 9001, customer, statutory or regulatory) as well as to continuously improve (Alshare et al., 2018).

B. Hypotheses Development

According to Talib et al. (2011), ineffective employee motivation lead to service quality challenges within the organisation. Parasuraman & Zeithaml (2002) add that understanding and improving service quality requires that internal employees are strongly motivated. Motivated employees would go the extra mile to relate to customers and save the business through commitment towards organizational improvement (Lai et al., 2018). Given the ultimate contribution of employee motivation to e-service quality, the following hypothesis is established.

H1: Employee motivation has an effect on e-service quality in Abu Dhabi municipality

According to Ng & Matanda (2009), knowledge sharing within the technology environment is essential to e-service quality and e-loyalty perception among company customers. Knowledge sharing permits engagement between members of the organisation to identify innovative ways and means of servicing the company customers (Yang, 2019). The institution of collaborative and knowledge sharing platforms has therefore, been considered as integral to the acceptability and availability of e-services from the perspective of technology acceptance (Wu et al., 2009). Given this inter-relationship, the second research hypothesis is presented as follows:

H2: Knowledge sharing an effect on e-service quality in Abu Dhabi municipality

Collaborative culture strongly aligns with knowledge sharing towards e-service quality (Wu et al., 2018). According to Chung (2006), collaborative culture changes everything within the organisations with regards to how common objectives are pursued. Chung (2006) asserts that collaboration permits openness, peering, sharing and acting by replacing the old tenants of business. Collaboration builds on the transaction cost models, and the development of a new perspective to explain e-Gov systems development, as intended in the present research (Chung, 2006). Given this literature, the following hypothesis is presented:

H3: Collaborative culture has an effect on e-service quality in Abu Dhabi municipality

Work motivation is a collection of internal and external factors that influence how employees perform and result in particular actions (Kim and Kim, 2020). Behaviors are frequently predicted using motivation. Since motivation varies greatly amongst people, it frequently needs to be paired with skills and external circumstances that have an impact on how employees behave and perform (Lily et al., 2017).

H4: Employee motivation has an effect on organizational excellence in Abu Dhabi municipality.

One of the corporate organisations' fastest-growing sectors is knowledge management systems. In the information economy we currently have, income and prosperity are mostly derived from the creation and dissemination of information and knowledge (Nawab,

Nazir, Zahid & Fawad, 2021). One of the processes that aids organisations in producing, organising, using, disseminating, and transforming crucial data and departmental expertise that are crucial for various management tasks like decision-making, problem-solving, learning, and strategic planning is known as knowledge management (Husseini and Fam, 2019 a).

H5: Knowledge sharing an effect on organizational excellence in Abu Dhabi municipality.

Additionally, cooperation is necessary since small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) or other companies can lack the resources necessary to achieve TBL performance (Lee and Klassen, 2008). Additionally, relationship governance-based collaboration infuses culture, guiding partner firms on the "basis of trust and continuation," and essentially eliminating transactional costs (Galpin et al., 2015; Paulraj et al., 2014). Culture is based on relational view (RV), which creates connections amongst dependent business partners to get an advantage over rivals.

H6: Collaborative culture has an effect on organizational excellence in Abu Dhabi municipality.

The consideration of e-service quality as an essential ingredient for business excellence has been registered in the quality management literature and available business excellence models (EFQM, 2018; Chang et al., 2009). According to Nemati et al. (2002), e-service quality contributes effectively to organizational excellence by ensuring that customers and other external stakeholders' expectations are met. Given these observations, the research hypotheses of the research are presented as follows:

H7: E-service quality has an effect on organizational excellence in Abu Dhabi municipality

By installing quality policy, a company is able to outline key measures and responsibilities in charge of quality implementation (Rashid & Aslam, 2012). Enforcing such policies is essential to steer the organisation to adhere to key quality standards necessary to achieve business excellence. Lasrado & Uzbek (2017) add that quality policy stipulates the quality vision and provide the strategies to achieve this stated vision. Given this literature support, the last hypothesis is presented as follows:

H8: Company quality assurance policy significantly moderate the effect of e-service quality on excellence in Abu Dhabi municipality.

Figure 1 shows the proposed conceptual framework based on the literature reviewed above. These practices were shortly discussed in the previous section. Employee motivation, internal knowledge and collaborative culture have the capacity of supporting the e-service quality and organizational excellence in Abu Dhabi municipality through company quality assurance policy. This research emphasizes on the capability of e-service quality in causing a positive effect on developing an organization and its performance.

Fig. 1: Research framework

III. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODS

The information required for this work was gathered using a questionnaire that was designed to evaluate the research model. It had inquiries that responders from the UAE could understand in English. It was broken down into two categories: a) it measured six key topics using a Likert scale with a scale of 1 to 5 (from strongly disagree to strongly agree); and b) it covered the respondents' demographic profiles and was scored using an ordinal or nominal scale.

An original sample of 335 was sought as mentioned in the research. However, due to the lack of full response in the pilot, the actual sample was adjusted to include 40% non-response rate. The survey was therefore sent to a total of 469 respondents, given an additional non-response rate. Out of the 469 emails sent out to randomly selected participants, a total of 404 responded. This marks about 20.6% over-subscription of the original sample size of 335. Against the actual sample size (ie 469) put up to cover non-response, the subscription rate stands at about 86.1% rate. Out of the 404 responses fully received, all of them had attempted the survey. However, five candidates did not provide consent on the initial page of the survey questionnaire. These five responses were removed. In addition, some of the candidates selected the option that they would not want to participate. A total of 43 cases fell into this category. In total, out of 404 cases, only 365 remained after taking into consideration responses. It is important to add that the survey was branched from the consent form to disallow those who selected "I do not consent" from participating. It is important to add that these responses were collected from a random selection of Abu Dhabi municipality workers within the sampling frame of HR level 12 and above. A cross-sectional view of the data was visually conducted whether the responses changed after the first half timeline of data collection. Any differences in the groups within the data would create an unintended impact on the analysis and interpretation of the research findings. For this purpose, a two-way test for the difference was used to help assess input accuracy. For standard checks the completed data were not evaluated as the Smart PLS does not obligatorily consider

the distribution of re-search data as a precondition for statistical testing (Hair et al., 2014).

A 5-point Likert scale was used to operationalize the items, with 1 denoting strong disagreement and 5 denoting strong agreement. The analysis was performed using Smart PLS Version 2.0. SEM was chosen as a statistical method because it provides a side-by-side study that produces accurate estimation. The participants consisted of 161 males and 76 females: making 67.9% and 32.1%, respectively. This data is in line with the Abu Dhabi municipality employee structure, without much evidence of a side-lined category. Since the probability sampling was implemented, the data may be considered as free of sample bias and capturing the format or profile within the population.

The results indicate that 21.9% of the respondents were within the ages of 18 and 25; 17.3% of them were between the age range of 26 to 30; 63 respondents amounting to 26.6% of the respondents were between the ages of 31 and 35; another 21.5% of respondents or 51 participants were within the age range of 36 to 40 years. The last two age ranges formed the lowest within the table; age range 41-50 years accounted for 9.3%, and age range 46 and above accounted for the remaining 3.4% of the respondents. Employees in the operational level of the organization accounted for 22.8% or 54 cases within the data; operational level recorded the highest number of employees about 60% or 143 participants; the lowest group was top management level with 40 participants or 16.9% of the total respondents. This structure slightly differs from the internal human resource structure of Abu Dhabi municipality where the operational staff form the base of the workforce, with larger numbers competed to the middle-level and top-level management personnel. The largest category in this demographic feature was those who have been with the organization for 11 to 15 years; this group accounted for 22.8% or 54 participants. This was followed by those who had spent less than 5 years in Abu Dhabi municipality (22.4%), and those who had spent between 6-10 year (21.1%). The last groups included those who were between 16 to 20 years (14.3%) in the organization, preceded by those who had spent 20 years and above.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics are presented in Table 1. Statistics presented in this table includes the minimum and maximum statistics. The mean statistics are also presented together with the skewness, and kurtosis statistics. The composite mean scores are as well presented in the table. For the

composite mean scores, Employee Motivation had the highest mean score of 3.874 (SD = .755). This was followed by Quality Policy with a means score of 3.875 (SD = .799). Service Quality followed with 3.873 (SD = .973), Organizational excellence with a mean of 3.866 (SD = .765), Knowledge Sharing (Mean = 3.656, SD = .850), and Collaboration Culture (Mean = 3.581, SD = .973).

	Mean	SD	Skew	Kurtosis
Employee Motivation	3.87	.049	-.536	-.334
Knowledge Sharing	3.66	.055	-.239	-1.037
Collaborative Culture	3.58	.063	-.188	-1.224
Service Quality	3.87	.048	-.472	-.364
Quality Policy	3.8645	.05189	-.531	-.507
Org Excellence	3.8655	.04969	-.460	-.009

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

B. Reliability and Validity

The reliability of the data was tested as part of the pilot research. According to Creswell (2007), reliability refers to the consistency in measuring a construct over repeated measures. One measure of reliability is the internal consistency measure, using the Cronbach Alpha reliability statistic (Saunders et al., 2012). For a construct to be statistically reliable, it must have an alpha score of 0.7 or above. Nonetheless, an alpha score of 0.5 and above may be considered satisfactory. The reliability statistics for the pilot survey are presented in Table 2. Among the six main dimensions, 3 constructs were within an acceptable range of

above .7 whilst the remaining 3 were satisfactory or above .5 even though below .7.

According to Creswell (2007), validity represents the appropriateness of what is to be measured. Validity includes, among others, the need for reliability (Saunders et al., 2012). For the pilot, validity was measured using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and tolerance levels. A tolerance level of above 0.10 signifies statistical significance, whilst a VIF level of below 10 indicate acceptability. For the data presented in Table 3, all the predictors within the model passed the multi-collinearity test with the main dependent variable as a test of model validity.

Dimension	n	Alpha	Remarks
Employee motivation	7	.725	Acceptable
Knowledge Sharing	7	.762	Acceptable
Collaboration Culture	7	.685	Satisfactory
Service Quality	7	.665	Satisfactory
Quality Policy	5	.587	Satisfactory
Organizational excellence	6	.710	Acceptable

Table 2: Composite Reliability Results

	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
EM	0.324	3.082
KS	0.232	4.316
CC	0.233	4.297
SQ	0.192	5.217
QP	0.325	3.080

Table 3: Multicollinearity Assessment

The distinction between constructs is described by the discrimination of validity (Urbach & Ahlemann, 2010). Building cross-loading and the discriminatory validity of the structures can both be assessed in two ways (Fornell & Larcker 1981). The value is derived using the first method when the AVE square root of a building is more than associated with other structures (Fornell and Larcker 1981). The value for the second technique (cross-loading) indicates

that there are more loads of objects than there are in the other buildings. These numbers demonstrate a measurement model's discriminating validity. Executing the Smart PLS software algorithm function led to discriminant validity values. The values for the measurement of descriptive validity determined using Fornell Larcker were shown in Table 4's results.

	CC	EM	IE	KS	QP	SQ
CC	0.776					
EM	0.798	0.722				
OE	0.849	0.801	0.730			
KS	0.882	0.803	0.792	0.730		
QP	0.821	0.763	0.792	0.792	0.746	
SQ	0.824	0.807	0.834	0.774	0.804	0.697

Table 4: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

C. Hypotheses Findings

The coefficient results in support of the extended model are presented in Table 5. For the other models, knowledge sharing is not a significant predictor of service quality for the model without marker; and service quality is not significant predictor or service excellence for the model with marker. For all the models, H5 or the test for moderation was not statistically significant. Considering

these results, the extended model is, arguably, considered as most appropriate for the testing of the research hypotheses as it presents a more stable predictive outlook and strongest explanatory power. It is important to mention, however, that the extended model exhibits the highest form of R² statistic, an indication of high correlations between the antecedents, but this was controlled with the presence of the marker variable as originally discussed.

	Path Coefficient	SD	T Statistics	P Values
EM -> ESQ	0.137	0.057	2.428	0.016
KS -> ESQ	0.188	0.047	4.008	0.000
CC -> ESQ	0.200	0.056	3.566	0.000
ESQ -> OE	0.605	0.040	15.140	0.000
EM -> OE	0.127	0.041	3.059	0.002
KS -> OE	0.142	0.038	3.742	0.000
CC -> OE	0.139	0.042	3.335	0.001
QP -> OE	0.069	0.036	1.893	0.059
Moderating Effect 1 -> OE	-0.007	0.034	0.214	0.831

Table 5: Hypotheses Results

For the relationship between the mediator and the dependent variable (ESQ -> OE), the P value of 0.000 and T statistics of 15.140 shows a significant effect with path coefficient value of 0.605. The results are illustrated in Table 5.

statistics of 3.059 shows a significant effect with path coefficient value of 0.127. The results are illustrated in Table 5.

For the effects of the three independent variables and institutional excellence, all are significant. The first relationship is KS -> OE has a P value of 0.000 and T statistics of 3.742 shows a significant effect with path coefficient value of 0.142. The second relationship is CC -> OE has a P value of 0.001 and T statistics of 3.335 shows a significant effect with path coefficient value of 0.139. The third relationship is EM -> OE has a P value of 0.002 and T

For the effects of the three independent variables e-service quality, all are significant. The first relationship is CC -> ESQ has a P value of 0.001 and T statistics of 3.566 shows a significant effect with path coefficient value of 0.200. The second relationship is KS -> ESQ has a P value of 0.000 and T statistics of 4.008 shows a significant effect with path coefficient value of 0.188. The third relationship is EM -> ESQ has a P value of 0.011 and T statistics of 2.428 shows a significant effect with path coefficient value of 0.137. The results are illustrated in Table 5.

Fig. 2: Structural Model

Table 5 shows the evaluation of the path coefficient with T statistics values and P values for the moderation of the variable quality policy assurance (PE) on the relationship between e-service quality and organizational excellence. The results revealed that the P value of 0.831 and the t statistics value of 0.214 revealed a none significant moderating effect. In addition, the effect of PE on the organizational excellence is not significant as well.

V. DISCUSSIONS

It is necessary to note that business excellence models perform two functions. The first is, they guide firms and institutions towards business excellence. And the second is, they conduct assessment or evaluation of the performance of firms (Sampaio et al., 2012; Talwar 2011). Guiding firms towards business excellence is the major function of business excellence models, and conduction of assessment is the minor function of business excellence models. On the need to improve business excellence, organizations usually conduct self-assessments to investigate the alignment between strategies and their excellent results (Dahlgard et al., 2013). Self-assessment is seen as an aspect of excellence measurement where the excellence results of the organization are compared with other originations to identify areas of strengths and weaknesses (EFQM 2018). According to Al Ameri (2011), business excellence models help improve the strategic position of the origination as well as the overall organizational performance.

The concept of motivation acts as a median item in the human learning process. If a company does not have the capability to motivate its workers, the expertise or skills within the company is not utilized virtually to the maximum (Ganta, 2014). It has therefore become the focus of every educational organization or company to discover the elements that can assist them to effectively provide motivation packages to their workers to enable the workers to perform their tasks efficiently (Osteraker, 1999; Dartey-Baah & Amoako, 2011). Motivation is an internal issue for human beings. Excellent pay and recognition are the most effective motivators for workers (Islam & Ismail, 2008). It is necessary that employees are involved in the decision-making process of selecting motivation packages for workers instead of allowing managers to be in charge of the entire decision-making process (Pardee, 1990). This is because what may motivate the manager is not necessarily what may motivate the employee.

Hu et al., (2007) establish in their research that knowledge is fragmental, and as such, dispersed in the minds of different employees. Therefore, establishing the internal sharing of knowledge in an organization or institution was provide well-organized procedures for the interchange of knowledge and interaction among staffs (Chen & Lin, 2021; Chen & Barnes, 2006; Fullwood et al., 2013). Internal sharing of knowledge enables an organization to integrate and pass on individual knowledge to better the company's organizational resources (Kwok & Gao, 2005). Through the process of knowledge sharing, the individual knowledge of staff can be gripped by other staffs

in the company. Thereby expanding the company's scope of internal organizational knowledge (Zhou & Lee, 2012).

E-service quality must contribute to business excellence in organizations. As public entities handle the complexities of socio-economic development, the use of e-services has remained essential (Jimenez et al., 2015). According to Clement & Selvam (2006) and Subhash & Jay (2004), service quality is a key driver of customer satisfaction and business excellence. Improving service quality does not only lead to happy customers but help ensure that the internal stakeholders are equally happy (Rachel et al., 2008; Birgit, 2009). Given this relationship, it is essential that both public and private enterprises consider it essential to promote service quality in the bid to achieve business excellence.

VI. CONCLUSION

In general, it has aided managers of the Abu Dhabi Municipality and the public sector to assess the quality of e-services in terms of organizational excellence. The Abu Dhabi Municipality ought to try to keep its staff in good relationships. The Abu Dhabi Municipality should also keep track of the knowledge gleaned from various sources in order to improve the operations. Due to its contribution to this field of study, the study has expanded in a way that is natural from earlier research on the quality of e-services.

The finding of this study offers important theoretical and practical implications. As far as the authors are aware, this study is the first study which attempts to assess organizational excellence from e-service quality perspective using measures that differ from SERQUAL (Parasuraman et al., 2005) and e-service quality (Ekaabi et al., 2020). The results show that employee motivation, knowledge sharing, and collaborative culture are significant antecedents of e-service quality even though e-service quality fails to significantly predict organizational excellence. Also, company quality assurance policy does not moderate the effect of e-service quality on excellence. This model can be used as a guide for academics who want to examine how well users perceive the quality of particular e-services as well as for website administrators and e-service managers to evaluate the effects of modifications on their ability to provide top-notch services. After reading the literature and taking the challenges into consideration, this innovative framework was created. The organization of organizational excellence in e-service quality was made possible by this framework. Additionally, this framework helped developers comprehend and assess the criteria for e-service quality. The relationship between the categories of the framework might be considered in future research. In order to validate this model, researchers might also look at similar features in various circumstances. This research has applied several tests such as the preliminary analysis (missing value analysis, assessment of outliers, normality test, multicollinearity, and descriptive analysis), demographic analysis (response rates and profiles of respondents), measurement modeling (reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity), structural model, and hypotheses testing (direct effect, mediation effect, and summary of

research hypotheses). It was recommended that the factors and challenges of service quality be further explored to identify key influencing factors that explain the lack of connection between e-service quality and service excellence.

Other studies can concentrate on verifying the model in other public sectors and other Arab nations. This work has evaluated the research model in Abu Dhabi Municipality in the United Arab Emirates. In addition, this research focused on the public sector only, leaving out the private sector. Additionally, the study assessed the e-services in terms of organizational excellence in the UAE but future work can replicate the examination in other locations.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Aburayya, A., Alshurideh, M., Al Marzouqi, A., Al Diabat, O., Alfarsi, A., Suson, R., ... & Salloum, S. A. (2020). An empirical examination of the effect of TQM practices on hospital service quality: an assessment research in UAE hospitals. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(9), 347-362.
- [2.] Aburayya, A., Alshurideh, M., Al Marzouqi, A., Al Diabat, O., Alfarsi, A., Suson, R., ... & Salloum, S. A. (2020). An empirical examination of the effect of TQM practices on hospital service quality: an assessment research in UAE hospitals. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(9), 347-362.
- [3.] Ahmed, F., Shahzad, K., Aslam, H., Bajwa, S. U., & Bahoo, R. (2019). The role of collaborative culture in knowledge sharing and creativity among employees. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences (PJCSS)*, 10(2), 335-358.
- [4.] Albalate, D., & Bel, G. (2020). Politicians, bureaucrats and the public-private choice in public service delivery: anybody there pushing for remunicipalization?. *Journal of Economic Policy Reform*, 1-19.
- [5.] Alshare, K. A., Lane, P. L., & Lane, M. R. (2018). Information security policy compliance: a higher education case research. *Information & Computer Security*. 26(1), 91-108.
- [6.] Bieñkowska, A., Tworek, K., & Zabłocka Kluczka, A. (2019). Information technology reliability influence on controlling excellence. Retrieved from: http://rabida.uhu.es/dspace/bitstream/handle/10272/15841/Information_technology.pdf?sequence=2.
- [7.] Chanana, L., Agrawal, R. & Punia, D. K. (2016). Service Quality Parameters for Mobile Government Services in India. *Global Business Review*, 17(1) 136-146.
- [8.] Chen, Y., & Lin, Z. (2021). Business intelligence capabilities and firm performance: A research in China. *International Journal of Information Management*, 57, 102232.
- [9.] Chiravuri, A., & Abdul, M. (2016). What determines the quality of e-Government Services in The UAE? Presenting A Framework. PACIS 2016 Proceedings. Paper 339. Retrieved from: <http://aisel.aisnet.org/pacis2016/339>.

- [10.] DPM. (2019). About the Department of Urban Planning and Municipalities. <https://www.dmt.gov.ae/en/adm>
- [11.] Ekaabi, M., Khalid, K., & Davidson, R. (2020). The service quality and satisfaction of smart policing in the UAE. *Cogent Business & Management*, 7(1), 1751904.
- [12.] Hair, J. F. J., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C., and Sarstedt, M. (2014). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Long Range Planning (46).
- [13.] Husseini, S.A and Fam, S.F., (2019). Integrating TQM practices and knowledge management to improve Malaysian banking, *Journal of Opcion*, 34, pp. 2899-2919.
- [14.] Husseini, S.A and Fam, S.F., (2019b). The Relationship Between Knowledge Management and Malaysian Digital Banking Reputation, *Journal of Opcion*, 34, pp. 2899-2919.
- [15.] Kim, J. H., & Kim, M. (2020). Conceptualization and assessment of E-service quality for luxury brands. *The Service Industries Journal*, 40(5-6), 436-470.
- [16.] Lai, I. K., Hitchcock, M., Yang, T., & Lu, T. W. (2018). Literature review on service quality in hospitality and tourism (1984-2014). *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*.
- [17.] Lasrado, F., & Uzbeck, C. (2017). The excellence quest: a research of business excellence award-winning organizations in UAE. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*.
- [18.] Lewis, B. D., Nguyen, H. T., & Hendrawan, A. (2020). Political accountability and public service delivery in decentralized Indonesia: Incumbency advantage and the performance of second term mayors. *European Journal of Political Economy*, 64, 101910.
- [19.] Li, Y. and Zhao, Z. (2018), "The dynamic impact of intellectual capital on firm value: evidence from China", *Applied Economics Letters*, 25(1), pp. 19-23.
- [20.] Lily, Ginting, P., Lumbanraja, P., & Siahaan, E. (2017). The antecedent of work motivation and the effect on the performance of civil servants with job satisfaction as moderating variable. *Journal of Public Relations Research* 17(4). 315–340.
- [21.] Urbach, N., and Ahlemann, F. (2010). "Structural equation modeling in information systems research using partial least squares", *Journal of Information technology theory and application*, 11(2), pp.5-40.
- [22.] Vasu, S. D. (2021). Rapid Internationalisation: The Critical Role Of Internal And External Factors On Capabilities And Business Strategy. *European Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 6(2).
- [23.] Wang, Z., Cai, S., Liang, H., Wang, N., & Xiang, E. (2018). "Intellectual capital and firm performance: the mediating role of innovation speed and quality". *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, pp.1-29.
- [24.] Wu, Y. L., Tao, Y. H., Yang, P. C., & Li, C. P. (2018). Developing a scale of e-service quality for blog. In *2009 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management* (pp. 1287-1291).
- [25.] Yang, F. X. (2017). Effects of restaurant satisfaction and knowledge sharing motivation on eWOM intentions: the moderating role of technology acceptance factors. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 41(1), 93-127.
- [26.] *Trans. Roy. Soc. London*, vol. A247, pp. 529-551, April 1955. (references)
- [27.] J. Clerk Maxwell, *A Treatise on Electricity and Magnetism*, 3rd ed., vol. 2. Oxford: Clarendon, 1892, pp.68-73.
- [28.] I.S. Jacobs and C.P. Bean, "Fine particles, thin films and exchange anisotropy," in *Magnetism*, vol. III, G.T. Rado and H. Suhl, Eds. New York: Academic, 1963, pp. 271-350.
- [29.] K. Elissa, "Title of paper if known," unpublished.
- [30.] R. Nicole, "Title of paper with only first word capitalized," *J. Name Stand. Abbrev.*, in press.
- [31.] Y. Yorozu, M. Hirano, K. Oka, and Y. Tagawa, "Electron spectroscopy studies on magneto-optical media and plastic substrate interface," *IEEE Transl. J. Magn. Japan*, vol. 2, pp. 740-741, August 1987 [Digests 9th Annual Conf. Magnetism Japan, p. 301, 1982].
- [32.] M. Young, *The Technical Writer's Handbook*. Mill Valley, CA: University Science, 1989.